

Digital Pedagogies, Learning Engagement, and Integrated Assessment

Dr. Vijayalakshmi R, Associate Professor, Amity University, Bengaluru.

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Abstract: ICT have taken the role of pedagogy in teaching and learning, and its variants had showed many difficulties to all the individuals of the society like adapting to online studies and schooling, work from home, shift to online or virtual world was indeed a difficult barrier for all the citizens. Last three years of education system had brought much difficulty to students or the learners including teachers and parents for adopting to technology for educational purpose as last three academic years had been on a virtual platform like online classes, online assignments, online presentations and online examinations, evaluation and assessment the education system had merely transferred from traditional teaching to online/ mobile teaching and learning process. Keeping this on mind this research paper tries to compare traditional teaching vs online teaching from learners' perspective or students' perspective. This research paper also looks into the positive and negative impacts of both traditional teaching and online teaching to draw the comparison. This research paper includes both qualitative and quantitative research methodology to draw out the conclusion.

Keywords: Traditional Teaching, Online Teaching, Student, Technology, Internet.

1. Introduction

Technology in today's world had tremendously changed the way of living, the living standards had become very easy. This development and internet development had helped citizens to overcome covid bane to some extent. As Rabindranath Tagore rightly said, "Don't limit a child to your own learning, for he was born in another time." Development and internet had given great helping hands for educational purpose during the times of covid this development had supported the educational system to run its role smoothly it indeed had made the education system ease and with the arrival and adaptation of online education many educational institutions had started complete online teaching programs for few programs though the adaption was tough to many learners, teachers and parents but it had stood the only option to all the learners. Now, technology as completely integrated with education. Looking into this development this research paper tries to compare and conclude the difference between traditional teaching vs online teaching.

2. Background of the study

Traditional Teaching:

Traditional teaching is defined as the education that takes place in a classroom with a teacher who drafts a lesson plan, develops it and delivers a lesson on a certain topic to learners. The instructor can utilize a variety of teaching methods, for example Grammar translation method, Direct method, Audio-lingual method, situational language teaching, total physical response, natural approach etc. according to the learner's level with the inclusion of chalk or whiteboard presentations, student presentations, group or pair work, and individual exercises or activities, to introduce knowledge.

Advantages:

- In person or one-on-one instruction is successful which results in higher levels of student engagement with teachers.
- Interpersonal skills will be developed by the learners through peer learning and communication skills.
- The traditional classroom teaching setting encourages student engagement and creates a suitable learning environment for other students.
- Extra circular activities like various clubs, events and tours by the institution will help the learners to have the best the learning process in the interested fields apart from studies.
- Continues monitor of teacher and feedback in traditional teaching will help in the progress of the learners where in online teaching mode the interactivity of the learners lacks.

- It also motivates kids to compete at a greater level.
- A conventional school's social setting is ideal for developing a child's character and individuality.

Disadvantages:

- It's difficult for a teacher to create a separate lesson plan for slow learners.
- Traditional teaching is sometimes bound by time.

Online teaching:

Online teaching is a type of distant learning that takes place through the help of internet. It can be teacher-led at a set time (synchronous) or student-led, with students going through the subject at their own leisure (asynchronous). Texts, power point, graphics, and videos may all be used to provide content and elements such as online evaluation and interactive activities can be included.

Advantages:

- Online teaching helps the teachers and learners to have flexibility in their learning time.
- The learner can create his/her own learning atmosphere in their respective homes to be active in learning process.
- As online teaching helps the learners to get access with many e-books and materials which help them to have easy access and 0 weight in carrying them.

Disadvantages:

- Students lack the discipline and necessary focus to study in a virtual classroom setting.
- Children's social contact, communication skills and development of social skills are also hindered by online learning.
- Students in an online teaching are also deterred from studying by their exposure and easy access to unpleasant information on the internet.
- learners develop issues like procrastinating and lack of self-discipline.
- Need of technology and internet access plays as major barrier to many learners.
- Learners face many distractions in online learning mode as they listen from their homes.
- Some practical subjects can't be taught in online mode of teaching.

Research Objectives

1. To critically evaluate Traditional Teaching vs Online Teaching.
2. To study the impact of online teaching method with the comparison of Traditional Teaching method on learners.
3. To recommend the outcome out of comparison and questionnaire from learners perspective.

3. Review of Literature

The chapter Review of literature in this research paper presents about various other research articles on the comparison traditional teaching vs online teaching. Each researcher in their respective research paper used different methodology to state the outcome in the comparison of traditional teaching vs online teaching and few researches also focused on teachers' perspective, learners' perspective of different level of learners. Online teaching mode became a major emerging area after the arrival of corona though virtual learning was present to some extent, but the wide spread of online education and various education apps had become famous only after the wide spread of corona in the world. Even many teachers are new to this online mode of education which made them took time to adapt from regular chalk and talk method or traditional teaching to online teaching.

Makarova Elena in her research paper titled "Effectiveness of traditional and online learning: comparative analysis from the student perspective" discussed the problems of effective learning in online teaching mode. The study explores the drawbacks and benefits of online teaching from university student perspective. The research paper follows both the

qualitative and quantitative methodology. The findings from the student's perspective had brought up the conclusion that the data demonstrate that respondents had a good attitude toward digital learning and that students are aware of the challenges to efficient distant learning, such as their laziness and incompetence.

Hayward Stephen and Pejsky Rex in their research titled "Term paper quality of online vs. traditional students" had used a blind grading process to test the learners from traditional teaching and online teaching from the learners of economics graduates the outcome proposed that there was no difference between the scores of traditional teaching and online teaching.

Stack steven Dr. in his research paper tried to focus on the learning outcomes in an online vs tradition course. The two limitations that the researcher had marked as limitation is (1) the possible problem of selection bias in which students choose their own method of course delivery, and (2) the relative lack of doctoral exams in the online section. The sample population was 64 learners from criminology classroom the outcome saw that both there was no difference of outcome between the traditional teaching and online teaching.

Alghazo Ali in his research paper titled "Learning Outcomes in an online vs traditional course" tried to compare the effectiveness of online and traditional teaching but by using the learner's final grade the researcher had used 2 detailed t test and the outcome proposed by the researcher is that there was no significant difference in the score or grades score by the learners and the researcher concluded that there is no difference between traditional teaching vs online teaching.

Hong Yun, Li Xiaolan, Lin yingwen, Xie Jun, Yan Xutong, Lin Zhengmei in their research paper titled "A Comparative Study of Online Education and Traditional Offline Education During COVID-19". The research paper conducted comparative analysis from teacher student survey on traditional teaching and online teaching the outcome proposed that both the teachers and students had agree that online teaching is not as effective as traditional teaching.

4. Methodology

The methodology used in this research by the research to study the impact of Traditional teaching method vs Online teaching method from learner's experience implies a detailed study and an organized study of various text from various books, e-books and e-sites. The methodology that has chosen by the research to draw out the comparison between Traditional teaching method vs Online teaching method involves population and sample of study, both quantitative study and qualitative study, face to face interactions, interviews, discussions were used to propose the outcome.

Population and sample size:

The sample population of 100 learners/students were chosen for the research by the research. The sample population of learners are from different levels like PUC/Intermediate, U.G and P.G. The learners chosen for the sample population are experienced by both Traditional teaching learning experience and Online teaching learning experience.

Qualitative and quantitative method:

The researchers in the research paper used both quantitate method and qualitative method to draw out the accurate outcome. Researchers employed quantitative method of data collection technique from questionnaires and statistical analysis from it. Researchers employed qualitative method like interacting with learners personally and mentioning their point of view and personal experience on Traditional teaching and online teaching to propose the accurate outcome.

Statistical Techniques:

The research in the research paper presented the outcome through the procedure of data collection from the questionnaire to bring out the accurate percentage after collecting the data pie charts are used by the research to bring the precise percentage from the collected data from learners.

Data Analysis and interpretation:

The researchers in the research paper performed in-depth analyses and interpretations of the acquired data using interview sessions and questionnaires. Learners/students who participated in the questionnaire and interview sessions are from PUC/Intermediate, Under graduates and Postgraduates. The learners/students had answered to the poll-based

questionnaire with their prior experience on Traditional teaching and Online teaching and with the best interests of their students in mind. The rubrics for the questionnaire were made up of four distinct alternatives that varied depending on the questions Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and strongly Disagree.

The data was analysed and presented in the form of pie-charts by the researchers in the research paper. Learners/students thoughts on each issue in the questionnaire were examined by researchers. The research paper outcome is the analysis based on the viewpoint of learners.

Survey and Interviews:

The researchers had surveyed learners/ students and conducted interviews with them to understand their point of view on Traditional teaching vs Online teaching and their experience with the respective teaching and learning mode.

Using the learners/students' opinions and their point of view while engaging with them in the interview and analysing the questionnaire, it was found out that all the learners have experience with both the teaching and learning experience. It was examined that out of 100 percentage 70 percentage learners did not feel online education as the best alternative for traditional teaching but as bounded by covid and updating of education system online education is playing a key role in present day.

5. Findings

In order to propose the outcome, all the data collected from questionnaire were gathered and entered in the excel sheet and the collected information is formed in to pie charts. The questions presented in the research paper follows the same chronology that had followed in the questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of 15 questions and 2 basic questions like Name, gender and education level. Based on these questions

- It was found out that: 57% male and 43% female.

- It was found out that 59% are from post graduate background, 37% under graduate background, 3% PUC/Intermediate background and 1% schooling background.

1. Do you have good knowledge with technology and study apps?

In the result of question 1, it was found out that 65% of learners agree that they have good knowledge with technology and study apps, 29% of learners strongly agree that that they have good knowledge with technology and study apps but whereas 6% learners disagree that have good knowledge with technology and study apps.

2. Did you face any hardships to adopt to technology for educational purpose?

In the result of question 2, it was found out that 42% of learners agree that they have faced hardships to adopt to technology for educational purpose. 39% of learners disagree that they have faced hardships to adopt to technology for educational purpose. 13% of learners strongly agree that they have faced hardships to adopt to technology for educational purpose but whereas 6% of learners strongly disagree that they have faced hardships to adopt to technology for educational purpose. We can observe that even though the learners who selected for the sample population belong to generation z 42% agree and 13% strongly agree that they felt it difficult to shift online education from traditional education.

3. Did you face difficulty to study in an online platform?

In the result of question 3, it was found out that 43% of learners agree that they have difficulty to study in an online platform. 30% of learners strongly agree that they have faced difficulty to study in an online platform but whereas 23% of learners disagree that they have faced difficulty to study in an online platform and only 4% of learners strongly disagree that they have faced difficulty to study in an online platform.

4. Do you think better results can be achieved through online learning?

In the result of question 4, it was found out that 47% of learners disagree with the statement that online learning achieves better results. 24% of learners strongly disagree with the statement that online learning achieves better results but whereas 23% of learners agree with the statement that online learning achieves better results and 6% of learners strongly agree with the statement that online learning achieves better results. We can see that 23% of learners agree and 6% of learners strongly agree the reason behind this is that they felt it easy to score in online education as few of them balance work and job. So, they supported online education.

5. Do you prefer online learning platform as the best option?

In the result of question 5, it was found out that 54% of learners disagree that online learning platform as the best option/alternative. 34% of learners strongly disagree that online learning platform as the best option/alternative but whereas 10% of learners agree that online learning platform as the best option/alternative and 2% of learners strongly agree that online learning platform as the best option/alternative.

6. Do you think teacher student interaction in online platform was more than traditional teaching method?

In the result of question 6, it was found out that 49% of learners disagree that online teaching have more teacher interactivity than traditional teaching method and 47% of learners strongly disagree that online teaching have more teacher interactivity than traditional teaching method but whereas 4% of learners agree that online teaching have more teacher interactivity than traditional teaching method the reason behind this is there faculty had tried their best possible way to interact this question also throws light that traditional teaching and learning will have great impact on teacher student interaction as face to face experience always will have greater influence on learners.

7. Did you feel the competitive spirit in online teaching platform?

In the result of question 7, it was found out that 57% of learners disagree that online teaching platform provokes competitive spirit and 33% of learners strongly disagree that online teaching platform provokes competitive spirit but whereas 10% of leaners agree that online teaching platform provokes competitive spirit.

8. Did you feel that there was a continues supervision by the teacher in the online platform like offline teaching method?

In the result of question 8, it was found out that 54% of learners disagree that online teaching/online platform have continues supervision by the teacher as like offline teaching method and 29% of learners strongly disagree that that online teaching/online platform have continues supervision by the teacher as like offline teaching method but whereas 16% of leaners agree that online teaching/online platform have continues supervision by the teacher as like offline teaching method and only 1% of learners strongly agree that online teaching/online platform have continues supervision by the teacher as like offline teaching method.

9. Do you think or did you face lack of interest or easy diversion in online platform due to easy access of data?

In the result of question 9, it was found out that 46% of learners strongly agree that they have faced lack of interest or easy diversion in online platform due to easy access of data and 37% of learners agree that they have faced lack of interest or easy diversion in online platform due to easy access of data but whereas 15% of learners disagree that they have faced lack of interest or easy diversion in online platform due to easy access of data and 2% of learners strongly disagree that they have faced lack of interest or easy diversion in online platform due to easy access of data.

10. Did you think that online mode of educational will provoke the interest to attend classes regularly?

In the result of question 10, it was found out that 49% of learners disagree that online mode of educational will provoke the interest to attend classes regularly and 21% of learners strongly disagree that online mode of educational will provoke the interest to attend classes regularly but whereas 24% of learners agree that online mode of educational will provoke the interest to attend classes regularly and 6% strongly agree that online mode of educational will provoke the interest to attend classes regularly/

11. Did you feel more stress when it was online based examination?

In the result of question 11, it was found out that 38% of learners disagree that they have felt stress during online based examination and 10% of learners strongly disagree that they have felt stress during online based examination but whereas 34% of learners agree that they have felt stress during online based examination and 18% of learners strongly agree that they have felt stress during online based examination.

12. Did you face irregular timetable during online teaching platform?

In the result of question 12, it was found out that 45% of learners agree that they have faced irregular timetable during online teaching platform and 34% of learners strongly agree that they have faced irregular timetable during online teaching platform but whereas 19% of learners disagree that they have faced irregular timetable during online teaching platform the reason is that due to online teaching it became easy to teachers and learners to schedule class at any point of time as there was no any fixed timings and 2% of learners strongly disagree that they have faced irregular timetable during online teaching platform.

13. Do you think that online teaching platform is a best alternative for traditional teaching method out of your experience?

In the result of question 13, it was found out that 40% of learners disagree that online teaching platform is a best alternative for traditional teaching method out of their experience and 30% of learners strongly disagree that online teaching platform is a best alternative for traditional teaching method out of their experience and 25% of learners agree that online teaching platform is a best alternative for traditional teaching method out of their experience and 5% of learners strongly agree that online teaching platform is a best alternative for traditional teaching method out of their experience.

14. Do you feel the connectivity of syllabus or the content is present as like the offline teaching mode?

In the result of question 14, it was found out that 50% of learners disagree that the connectivity of syllabus or the content is as same as the offline teaching mode and 17% of learners strongly disagree that the connectivity of syllabus or the content is as same as the offline teaching mode but whereas 30% of learners agree that the connectivity of syllabus or the content is as same as the offline teaching mode and 3% of learners strongly agree that the connectivity of syllabus or the content is as same as the offline teaching mode.

15. Do you think Shared learning experience among learners or communication skills/ social interaction will develop through online teaching?

In the result of question 15, it was found out that 44% of learners disagree that online teaching mode will develop learning experience among learners or communication skills/ social interaction and 25% of learners strongly disagree that that online teaching mode will develop learning experience among learners or communication skills/ social interaction but whereas 28% of learners agree that online teaching mode will develop learning experience among learners or communication skills/ social interaction this shows us how important peer learning and classroom learning engages students to develop their social skills and 3% of learners strongly agree that online teaching mode will develop learning experience among learners or communication skills/ social interaction.

6. Conclusion

After analyzing all the responses to the questionnaire by the learners, we can conclude from the responses that even though most of the learners belong to generation z and 65% of learners agree that they have good knowledge with technology and study apps, 29% of learners strongly agree that that they have good knowledge with technology and study apps out of 100% but whereas only 10% of learners agree that online learning platform as the best option/alternative and 2% of learners strongly agree that online learning platform as the best option/alternative. When the researches have examined the reason for this through the questionnaire it was found out that irregular time-table, no continues supervision, lack of interest in online mode of teaching, easy diversion due to easy access of data and lack of competitive spirit.

According to the findings of the study, out of 100% learners 54% of learners disagree and 34% of learners strongly disagree that online learning platform as the best option/alternative but with the spread of corona virus online teaching mode had become the best possible option to reach to the corners of the world in the aspect of education.

Implication

Apart from the learner's perspective they are other factors that influence the result of the sample for example like external factors like surrounding barriers in the place the learner listens, network issues, absence of peer learning, absence of audio- video aids during online teaching as it alone acts as a bridge to the learners to connect with the content and health issues because of over usage of online teaching like headache, sight and lack of continues feedback by the teachers. Moreover, learner's lack of interest to online mode of teaching and parents' role and their perspective also plays a key role in the development of online teaching mode. Hence, even though online mode of learning is not a best option by most of the learners, but online mode of learning helped the teaching learning process to continue in an easy way without any desist.

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